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Recruiting Apprentices - The Experience of On-boarding Practices in the Swiss Public Transportation Sector

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Abstract

The professional socialization in a training company is a great challenge for young people. At the same time, they have to adapt to new organizational structures, integrate into a new workplace and competently master new tasks. Successful vocational socialization depends not only on the interests, abilities, and expectations of the young people but also on the company and its on-boarding practices. The aim of on-boarding measures is to help newcomers to get to know the company's structures and to facilitate their socialization into the culture of the company. Based on findings of an in-depth explorative case study within the public transportation sector in Switzerland, that included interviews with all stakeholders involved in apprenticeship training, the paper will address the practice of on-boarding in apprenticeship training and arrive at conclusions about innovative approaches.

Keywords

professional socialization, apprenticeship, workplace learning, case study

1 Introduction

About 73% of each cohort leaving compulsory education in Switzerland start an apprenticeship, the majority within the dual system of education. Most of the young adults are between 15 and 16 years old when they enter workplaces for a few days a week. In general, there is a high commitment of employers in the country towards training apprentices and most of the young adults find an apprenticeship placement.

However, the professional socialization in a training company is a great challenge for young people. At the same time, they have to adapt to new organizational structures, integrate into a new workplace and competently master new tasks. Successful vocational socialization depends not only on the interests, abilities, and expectations of the young people but also on the company and its onboarding practices. Research has shown that a high perceived fit between the young people's interests and abilities and their career choice can be seen both as a prerequisite and a consequence of successful vocational socialization (Singer et al., 2013). In Switzerland, within about 20-25% of all apprenticeships apprentices decide to terminate their contract, mostly in the first year of training (Kriesi et al., 2016). Although many of these apprentices eventually

complete another apprenticeship, the process of terminating a contract is often a harmful experience for young people and also causes costs for the enterprise that may be avoided by investing more in on-boarding measures (Schörger et al., 2013). Research has shown that a positive socialization ideally leads to high work motivation and work satisfaction and a long-lasting organizational commitment, by that reducing fluctuation (Gagné & Deci, 2005; Saks & Gruman, 2018).

Vocational socialization can be defined as the influence of work on the personality (Frese, 1983). It is also a process, in which a (young) person learns abilities, knowledge, attitudes, values and behaviour to work and learn as an integrated member of an enterprise (Feij, 1998; Singer et al., 2014). Working in a specific occupation requires specialized activities, for which the development of special (motor and intellectual) abilities and general social orientations, such as willingness to cooperate is necessary (Lempert, 2006).

On the learners' side, a positive parental relationship, a large amount of prior knowledge about the training company and a high degree of confidence in making the right career choice are key resources for successful vocational socialization, which in turn fosters the development of the perceived fit between the interests and abilities of young people and their career choice, respectively if the subjective self-concept of a person fits the subjectively perceived requirements of the environment (Singer et al., 2014).

On the training company side, the term "on-boarding" has become established in the research literature recently to describe the role a training company plays in socializing and integrating newcomers into its organizational structures and culture during the recruitment process (Klein & Polin, 2012). The term "on-boarding" can be distinguished from socialization in that it refers exclusively to formal and informal measures initiated by the company to facilitate the adjustment and integration of newcomers (Klein & Polin, 2012). The aim of on-boarding measures is to help newcomers to get to know the company's structures and to facilitate their socialization into the culture of the company (Klein & Polin, 2012).

The paper will address the following research questions:

1. How are on-boarding measures helping young adults in the public transportation sector in their early socialization in the workplace?
2. How is on-boarding organized within the public transportation sector in Switzerland?
3. Which attitudes, beliefs and values are found among the trainers involved in on-boarding measures?
4. How do the apprentices experience their onboarding?

Based on findings of an in-depth explorative case study within the public transportation sector in Switzerland, that included interviews with all stakeholders involved in apprenticeship training, the paper will address these questions and arrive at conclusions about innovative on-boarding practices for apprentices.

2 Professional socialisation and on-boarding practices

Professional socialisation in a training company is a major challenge for young people (Barabasch et al, 2020). At the same time, they have to get to know new organisational structures, integrate themselves into a new workplace and competently master new tasks. Successful professional socialisation depends not only on the interests, skills and expectations of the young people, but also on the company and its on-boarding practices. In the following, we will discuss the theoretical foundations and selected research findings for professional socialisation and on-boarding.

Professional socialisation begins when learners in vocational education and training start working in their teaching company. This is the time when young people move from a school

environment that is quite structured in terms of social interaction, time and subject matter to a much less structured workplace (Singer et al., 2013). In their professional socialisation in the workplace, learners have to deal with unknown tasks and role expectations (Ganser & Hinz, 2007). Professional socialisation can be defined as the influence of work on personality (Frese, 1983). It is also a process in which a (young) person learns skills, knowledge, attitudes, values and behaviour in order to work and learn as an integrated member of a company (Feij, 1998; Singer et al., 2013). Working in a particular profession requires specialised activities for which the development of specific (motor and intellectual) skills and general social orientations, such as willingness to cooperate, are necessary (Lempert, 2006).

According to Singer and colleagues (2013), successful professional socialisation is characterised by a high degree of fit between a young person and his or her chosen profession, if the young person's subjective self-image corresponds to the subjectively perceived demands of the environment. In this context, the term fit refers to the correspondence between a person's interests and skills and his or her vocational training. In analogy to the stage-environment fit theory of Eccles and colleagues (Eccles et al., 1993), fit is not defined in terms of the profession, company or workplace, but holistically in terms of the apprenticeship as a form of training for a specific occupation. The perceived fit develops continuously in a dynamic and reciprocal process, because both the working environment and the learners change because of the professional socialisation in the training company (Singer et al., 2013; Solinger et al., 2013).

Solinger et al. (2013) found in their study that even if a large part of the adaptation in the form of attraction and selection mechanisms had taken place before the time of entering an apprenticeship, there are additional dynamic adjustments during the beginning months (Solinger et al., 2013). The question of under what conditions young people succeed in professional socialization during the first phase of their vocational training and how they experience this has hardly been researched to date. This may be due to the fact that the question only arises in countries with a dual vocational training system and that the focus of vocational training research there has been placed differently to date (Singer et al., 2013). The results of a longitudinal study by Singer et al. (2013) show that, as areas of professional socialisation, integration into the working group in the training company and mastering company tasks positively influence changes in the perceived fit between oneself and the training place. On the one hand, this results in the fact that it is central to successful professional socialisation that young people are able to fulfil the professional requirements of their apprenticeship (Singer et al., 2013). On the other hand, successful integration into the working group and thus the establishment of positive social relationships is just as important for experiencing a high degree of fit (Singer et al., 2013). According to their findings, a positive parental relationship, confidence in making the right career choice and sufficient prior knowledge about the training company are important resources for successful professional socialisation. Furthermore, if the degree of self-regulation of the young people was low it had a negative effect on their mastering of company tasks but not on their integration into the working group (Singer et al., 2013).

With regard to our research questions, the findings on the career choice process as a resource for successful social integration are of particular importance. Young people, who were confident in their choice of occupation and had acquired a great deal of knowledge about the training company during their career choice process, found it easier to integrate into the working group and had less difficulty in coping with in-company tasks (Singer et al., 2013). By acquiring prior knowledge, young people seem to be able to form a realistic idea of what to expect in the training enterprise. This enables them to prepare mentally for the transition, which in turn makes it easier for them to adapt to the new environment and the new requirements (Singer et al., 2014). In addition to a high perceived fit between the young person and his or her apprenticeship, Nägele and Neuenschwander (2016) also found that personality traits, such as reliability, help for socialisation in the training company.

A successful socialisation process is further dependent on the on-boarding practices of the training companies, which support young people both in the process of choosing a profession and in starting an apprenticeship. On-boarding can be distinguished from socialisation in that it refers exclusively to formal and informal measures initiated by the company to facilitate the adaptation and integration of newcomers (Klein & Polin, 2012). Through targeted on-boarding strategies, a company can support learning and adaptation processes during job entry (Klein & Polin, 2012). It is important that newcomers receive the information and advice they need, which can be achieved through the provision of specific information and the allocation of sufficient and appropriate resources.

From a talent development perspective, on-boarding also offers training companies the opportunity to realise a return on investment in the recruitment process and ensure that newcomers become quickly engaged and productive (Becker & Bish, 2019). Following the theory of human capital it can be assumed: The sooner newcomers can learn company-specific knowledge, understand and recognize the culture and unique aspects of the organization, the sooner they can contribute to the success and competitive advantage of the organization (Klein et al., 2015). Considering that the term "on-boarding" refers primarily to measures taken to facilitate the entry into a new company, these measures are designed to help learners to take on a role within the company as quickly as possible that suits both their own needs and those of the organisation (Klein et al., 2015).

Klein and Heuser (2008) have defined three main purposes of on-boarding practices: Practices that help to inform the newcomer, those that welcome him or her and those that guide him or her. These three on-boarding categories form the framework for the Inform-Welcome-Guide (IWG), which is applicable to all organisations, workplaces and contexts (Klein & Heuser, 2008). The inform category covers a wide range of specific practices and is divided into three subcategories: communication, resources and training (Klein & Heuser, 2008). The subcategory communication covers both communications from the company to newcomers (e.g. a welcome letter) and opportunities for dialogue (e.g. a planned phone call). The subcategory resources covers practices beyond direct communication that provide resources to new employees to help them adapt (e.g. FAQs on hiring new employees on the company intranet) (Klein & Heuser, 2008). The subcategory training covers planned programmes to facilitate the systematic acquisition of knowledge and skills that a newcomer needs to know (e.g. orientation training, induction events). The category welcome includes activities aimed at celebrating the new employee, expressing appreciation for joining the organisation and giving him or her the opportunity to meet other members of the organisation (e.g. a welcome dinner) (Klein & Heuser, 2008). This category includes practices that address the emotional needs of newcomers and help them to develop social capital (Klein & Polin, 2012). The third category includes those practices that aim to assist actively and directly newly hired persons (e.g. by an assigned employee) to help them with their transition "from a naive outsider to an effective insider" (Klein & Heuser, 2008, p. 265).

Little research has been done so far on on-boarding practices and their effectiveness. For instance, Klein et al. (2015) examined on-boarding practices of ten companies from different industries, interviewing managers and HR professionals as well as employees. Another purpose of their study was to test the IWG-framework. The results show that for all five IWG-categories, the number of practices offered (or experienced) was positively correlated with increased socialisation of newcomers (Klein et al., 2015). It turned out that the socialization becomes easier with an increasing amount of different on-boarding practices and their positive experience by newcomers (Klein et al., 2015). Employees tended to mention practices more frequently in some IWG-categories than in others, while all five IWG-categories were experienced more formally than informally (Klein et al., 2015). In addition, newcomers found practices more helpful if they were mandatory rather than voluntary (Klein et al., 2015).

The timing of on-boarding practices also seems to play an important role. However, the optimal timing of practices is more complex than simple "the earlier the better" (Klein et al., 2015). The optimal timing for a particular on-boarding practice may depend on the needs of the new employee, the type of practice and the number of offers. Other studies provide evidence that organisations have different types of employees on board in different ways. (Klein et al., 2015). For example, Fondas and Wiersema (1997) found that the broad socialisation practices used to on-board managers often differ from those used at lower levels (more informal, non-sequential and individual). Furthermore, in a recent descriptive survey of on-boarding practices conducted by the Society for Human Resource Management (SHRM, 2011), they found that slightly less than half of the organisations persons surveyed handled on-boarding differently for entry, mid- and senior level employees. However, which specific practices within the IWG categories are most effective in certain situations has not yet been investigated (Klein et al., 2015).

To our knowledge, there is also little research evidence on on-boarding practices in recruiting apprentices and their entry into the new company. Barabasch et al. (2020) found in their case study on learning cultures at the Swiss communications company Swisscom that young people are supported in their transition from the highly structured school to the less structured work environment by an introduction week, the 'First Steps Week'. During this week apprentices are introduced to the companies learning culture, learn how to use technical tools and gain initial insights into company concepts and organisational structures. In Switzerland, however, training companies play a key role not only when it comes to starting an apprenticeship, but also in young people's process of choosing a profession. Even during the upper school years, training companies, in cooperation with compulsory schools and regional vocational information centres, organise information events to support young people in their process of choosing a profession. Training companies also offer young people the opportunity to do an introductory apprenticeship (Schnupperlehre) so that they have the opportunity to obtain a realistic picture of the everyday working life in a company (Singer et al., 2013; Nägele & Neuenschwander, 2016). This is meant to give young people the opportunity to experience both the technical work content and their direct working environment with co-workers before they start their apprenticeship. This is essential to give young people the opportunity to form a comprehensive and realistic idea of their potential apprenticeship place (Singer et al., 2013; Nägele & Neuenschwander, 2016). To our knowledge, however, there are no studies on the effectiveness of various on-boarding practices both in the context of the process of choosing a profession and of starting an apprenticeship.

3 Methodology

The firm "login" provides VET training for apprentices that work in the public transportation sector. It cooperates with 50 partner-enterprises of the sector, for which they organize their VET training. A comprehensive case study (Yin, 2014; Yin & Davis, 2007) within various Swiss public transportation enterprises that train apprentices in an innovative manner has been conducted during 2018 and 2019. Participants represent the main stakeholders in workplace training: Apprentices, workplace trainers, personnel that directly works with apprentices such as coaches, as well as persons representing different levels of VET management.

The main data source were 60 semi-structured interviews with persons representing all groups of people involved in workplace training. Furthermore 18 site visits at different working (and learning) venues were conducted. Data collection was completed by document analysis of VET-related documents of the enterprises. Participants for the interviews and locations for site visits were selected by the team of researchers together with a VET manager at each enterprise. The cooperation in the selection of interview partners lead to a flexible continuing enlargement of the sampling in a function of theoretical sampling leading to data saturation, respectively to

a profound understanding of the cases. The interviews followed a general interview guideline aimed at finding out about daily work, regular tasks, successes and difficulties, the organization of VET programs, support by workplace trainers, as well as attitudes, values and beliefs regarding the workplace training.

Data were analysed by a content analysis (Kuckartz 2016). Two coders coded the entire material, supported by the software MAXQDA. The material was structured according to individual cases and categories representing different research topics (Kuckartz, 2016). In an iterative process, the narratives were coded according to emerging themes and regularly discussed by the research team to ensure the reliability and validity of the data. In this way, a comprehensive and detailed system of categories was derived. The analysis of the coded segments lead, among others, to a display of on-boarding practices and how they are experienced by apprentices and perceived by coaches and management.

4 Findings: On-boarding in the Swiss public transportation sector

Recruitment and on-boarding receive increasing attention in human resources and training departments at enterprises. The examples from login indicate how communication, resources and training are viewed and practiced.

4.1 Communication

In order to ensure that the expectations of the apprentices are matching reality, communication about the content of the apprenticeship and job opportunities afterwards, just as much as further qualification options, need to be clearly communicated. This helps to prevent that young people sign several apprenticeship contracts, but only start one apprenticeship or drop out of the apprenticeship, because their expectations are not met. It is further important to communicate about possibilities for employment within the public transportation sector and the general expectations of enterprises that apprentices would remain in the company as regular employees after graduating from their apprenticeship.

At first, however, enterprises need to reach out to pupils and show that an apprenticeship is an attractive option. The use of social media becomes increasingly important in this phase.

Young people can apply via ‘WhatsApp’; they can photograph their CV and send it. We check, whom we have in the pool of applicants and call candidates. And when someone feels he or she has an interest in informatics and sends us a video instead of a standard application, this is also possible. We need to be open and pick people up where they stand, how they tick. (Management)

The generation Z is regarded as a generation that communicates and responds much more to being approached by social media, expects to have flexible and creative possibilities to express themselves and communicate with others. They prefer individualized and pragmatic solutions over formalism and strictness. Companies have realized that the most suitable apprentices may be found more easily, if the flexibility towards other forms of communication is increased.

4.2 Resources

Also, in terms of advertising apprenticeships, strategies have been adjusted to communicate better with pupils. This requires a wider portfolio of measures to reach out, which can be more cost intensive.

We have adapted our recruitment to today’s needs among young people and communicate over various channels. In the past, it was sufficient to place a poster

somewhere and afterwards we waited for the applications to float in. The challenge today is to use social media platforms, videos or whatever. We have today widened our portfolio of measures and do much more to advertise our apprenticeships than 5-10 years ago. (head of training department)

Not just the ways in which pupils are approached is decisive for their application, but also the incentives offered throughout an apprenticeship.

I think it is important that the apprenticeship is a ‘cool’ one, also with advantages, such as the gratis abonnement for our public transport system. However, this is also offered in other enterprises and industries. Very good guidance and trust are key, that one knows that somebody is there for them, if problems arise. That one feels recognized and appreciated and can work independently. The trial of an apprenticeship (‘Schnupperlehre’) is very popular, because pupils come to us and try out typical work situations. They are impressed that they were allowed to work for two hours at the counter or the workbench. This is very popular. (head of training department)

While soft factors can be communicated, experiencing them would be key. Also, the imagination how work looks like in various jobs is enhanced when tasks can already be performed. With a short trial of an apprenticeship for one to five days (‘Schnupperlehre’), pupils can have a first glance or collect prior experiences and impressions of the daily work of an apprentice. This helps them in their decision making about an apprenticeship, but also provides the enterprise with an impression about the young person.

4.3 Training

Young people are increasingly interested in further qualification options and often enterprises are supportive. There are a number of possibilities that apprentices can make use of, especially, if they are performing well. Among them are internal training programs, language courses, rotations into enterprises or departments, where one wishes to gain work experience, or the support with resources for individuals, groups or teams. It also goes beyond the apprenticeship with training options provided for those, who are willing to remain with the enterprise.

The best apprentices are those, who want to acquire the vocational baccalaureate as their first goal after the apprenticeship, either in part-time or full-time. It depends what the enterprise is offering them and I think, it became more flexible over the years. Those, who have acquired the vocational baccalaureate want to study and it is difficult to predict, whom we want to keep afterwards, to know who wants to stay at the company for a longer time. Therefore, we do not want too many of those, who change to somewhere else, outside of the public transportation system. (head of training department)

5 Conclusion

Although, the large majority of young people in Switzerland still chooses an apprenticeship after compulsory schooling, their interest in developing themselves further via graduating from an institution of higher VET, a university of applied science or a university has increased. More applicants for apprenticeships at Login are asking how the enterprises are supporting their further development. The communication channels used at all stages of the on-boarding process have increased and include various forms of more creative expressions, such as videos, and require more flexibility of enterprises to engage in new forms of exchange. The advantage is

that individuals are given a chance to be taken into consideration, because they found their individual way to express and introduce themselves – an opportunity that may help to find the best matches in about 35 different apprenticeships offered at login.

Reaching out to pupils via a variety of social media, letting them experience what it means to be an apprentice, offering meaningful further qualifications and the incentive to take somewhat individualized routes through an apprenticeship in the interest of their personal competence development, while at the same time appearing authentic and trustful, helps to be successful with ones on-boarding measures. While on-boarding has become more complex today, it also provides more chances to find good matches between personal expectations and capacities and available apprenticeships and jobs.

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